

LINGUOCULTUROLOGY AND ITS BASIC PRINCIPLES.

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Sultanova Gulasal Nizomitdinovna

*Master student of Uzbekistan State World languages University
Chilanzar district ,178-Specialized State school,English teacher*

Abstract *This article provides theoretical background analysis to linguoculturology as a modern scientific discipline ,its interdisciplinary character, the role of linguoculturology among other branches of linguistics.It describes different definitions of linguists ,how this field is developing and the connection with other subjects.*

Keywords: *linguoculturology,phraseological units,spiritual,mankind,cognitive,ethnolinguistics,aesthetic,peculiarity.*

Introduction In modern life,knowing foreign language is very requirement all over the world.Everyone belongs to a specific culture that includes national traditions,language , customs,history and literature.When learning a language ,it is very important to know not only the words and idioms ,but also the origin,culture worldview,lifestyle and customs of the country of the target language.Linguoculturology as a special field of science has already given many productive concepts in modern linguistics.Learning language and culture of any nation we can understand how they influence each other and they are closely connected with each other.

Linguoculturology is a new branch of linguistics which deals with the culture of different countries and nations and it is reflected in the language.This relatively new field of linguistic research but it expanded rapidly among linguists and until now a lot of linguists worked and there are many books about it .Every scientists gave their explanation and notions about linguoculturology.One of them V.N.Telia which is known with his school as “Moscow school of linguocultural analysis of phraseological units” wrote Linguoculturology as”a study aimed at investigating and describing the correlation between language and culture in scope of modern culture national self-consciousness and its sign representation”(1996).V.V.Vorobyev said that it is”an integrated scientific discipline studying correlations and interactions between culture and language in their functioning”(2008) V.V.Krasnykh considers “Linguoculturology is a discipline studying manifestation,reflection and fixation of culture in the language and discourse”.(2003)If we enter to this

field ,we can find different notions and definitions but the main and central idea is Linguoculturology studies connection between culture and language.

According to the researchers this notion was found in the last quarter of the twentieth century and this term linguoculturology appeared in connection with research conducted by the Moscow School of Phraseology,led by V.N.Telia .After that all linguists point out that the roots of this theory go back to V.von.Humboldt.In the ninetenth century V.vonHumboldt laid the foundation for the field of linguoculturology with his book *The Structure of Language and its Influence on the Spiritual Development of Mankind* ,noting the relationship between language and national characteristics.He wrote following notions:"Different languages represent different worldviews in practice to their characteristics,their influence on thinking and feeling", "The specific features of language affect the identity of a nation ,so language in depth study should include everything that history and philosophy relate to the inner world of man".(1834)He understood a language as a spiritual power.According to the words of V.Humboldt language is the world lying between the outer life and inner world of a man.All scientists saw different ways of feelings and different languages through this way and this idea was developed by L.Weisgerber,H.Glins and H.Hols.

I mentioned that Linguoculturology is totally new discipline and there is no periodization and evolution but V.A.Maslova divided it in two periods.The first period consists of V.Humboldt`s,E.Sapir`s,B.Whorf`s and Russian linguist A.A.Potebnya`s works about linguoculturology.The second period started last years of 20th century and since this years it was the independent branch of linguistics.

Linguoculturology is closely linked with other subjects like Ethnolinguistics, Cognitive Linguistics,Country Studies,Linguoconceptology,History of the Language,Lexicology,Stylistics,Comparative Linguistics,History,Sociology,Anthropology,Philosophy,Theology and Culturology.I will share some of consideration results between Linguoculturology and other subjects.

There are close link between Linguoculturology and Ethnolinguistics.Initially, I should say that,before learning any sphere in the language ,we must address ethnic culture of this language .So scientists also learned ethnolinguistics to compare and to find more information in Linguoculturology.Ethnolinguistics studies the relationship between the nonlinguistic cultural behavior or customs and a language.From this definition we can understand that,Linguoculturology and Ethnolinguistics are almost same but ethnolinguistics studies only national specifics of the language

but Linguoculturology is more broad than Ethnolinguistics and it studies national specifics and world culture, its reflection in the language. According to V.A. Maslova, "cultural linguistics is a science that arose at the intersection of linguistics and culturology. This is not simple discipline" addition "of linguistics and cultural studies, but a new independent direction that should be studied in depth. Such a study presupposes, first of all, an analysis of the main stages of the formation of the development of that system with a glance which is called "cultural linguistics". This discipline associated with philosophy, national character, mentality. It is a kind of body of knowledge about the national and cultural specifics, the organization of the content of speech communication". (2007)

Another subject Cognitive Linguistics is closely connected with Linguoculturology. We know that Cognitive Linguistics studies relationship between language, mind and sociocultural experience. Any notion or any words in Linguoculturology depends on our mind and we discuss it in our mind then concept can appear in our mind about this word. The fact that the main components of the content of culture—the accumulation and processing of information obtained in the process of human activity, are functions of public consciousness. It creates images of everyday consciousness and the secondary transformation of mental content serves as a source of creative worldview, developing forms of primary development of the world." Cognitive linguists argue that concept is a part of our general knowledge about the world, a unit of the conceptual system reflecting the human cognitive activity. From this perspectives of linguoculturology "concept" is defined as a basic unit of culture, its core, a mental, cultural and nationally specific unit characterized by an array of emotional, expressive and evaluative components; a constituent part of the national conceptosphere". (Ashurova D. U. M. R. Galiyeva 2019.)

Vividly seen that, Linguoculturology and Country Studies are linked closely. Country Study studies foreign languages in comparison with the native language. Clearly, different information about a particular state, taught in the process of teaching the foreign language, is called country study. Education by means of a foreign language presupposes knowledge of the culture, history, religions and traditions of the country of the studied language. This term appeared firstly in E.M. Vereshagin and G.V. Kostomarov's books in 1971 and 1973. Linguists worked with this field because they need to compare native language with another foreign languages. From this information we can understand learning foreign languages opens doors to other cultures.

Another discipline is connection between Linguoculturology and Text Linguistics. Of course, connection between language and culture are most clearly seen in any texts. For example, if we want to get information about some

languages and to know specific data about it we usually look at their fictional books. This fictional book can give us sociocultural information and readers can understand it from writer's conceptual world picture. Authors use cultural, national, emotional words, phraseological units, historical elements, proverbs, myths and other important data in his /her work and readers so a lot of linguists analyse languages in fictional texts. Overall, we can give a lot of examples about connection of Linguoculturology and other subjects.

The main object of the study of Linguoculturology is the relationship and interaction of culture and language in the process of its functioning. The object of linguoculturology is the study of the interaction of language, which is a translator of cultural information, culture with its attitudes and preferences and the person who creates this culture using the language. Linguoculturology studies the national forms of being of society, reproduced in the system of language communication and based on the cultural values of a specific historical community. The most important task of linguoculturology and its characteristic distinguishing feature is the systematic representation of the culture of the people in its language. Linguoculturology explores the linguistic picture of the world, gives a systematic description of the facts of language and culture in their interaction and interrelation.

Linguoculturology as a subject requires from the teacher to introduce students not only to knowledge of the word, but also to the phenomenon of material and spiritual culture, which reflects the history of the people, their mentality in the cultural and historical environment that forms the linguistic personality. Through exercises containing linguistic and culturological material, the teacher will be able to help create a linguistic picture of the world, know the vocabulary, idioms and texts that reflect the culture of the people. Today, the importance of linguocultural education, ensuring the spiritual and moral development of the individual, the formation of linguocultural self-identification as a necessary component of its ideological potential and the conditions for integration into world culture.

The interrelation of language and culture is one of the basic concepts of the linguoculturological concept of language learning. This question can be considered in three aspects:

- 1) language as an indicator of the general culture of a person, his speech culture and culture of communication.
- 2) language as a phenomenon of culture and as a treasury of the culture of a people, its keeper and means of transmission from one generation to another.
- 3) language in its aesthetic function as a means of creating literature, one of the most important components of culture.

Linguoculturology is associated with culture-oriented linguistics as a system of solving ruling principles of general education and humanitarian task, but besides it linguoculturology possessing the culture with all its self-belonging peculiarities. Since the last two decades of the twentieth century the term "Linguoculturology" has been often used with the term "culture –through-language studies". Linguoculturology pays attention onto the reflection of spiritual state in the language of a man in the society. This is mentioned in Bashurina's work which she mentioned changing the shape of system of didactic coordinates instead of systems "teaching a language –acquaintance with culture" in the center of attention stands interrelation between communicative competence with linguoculturology and culture –oriented linguistics in the system of "teaching a language –acquaintance with culture-teaching a language". Telia, Maslova and other linguists created this sources.

During the last time on the method or representations of concepts, methods peculiar to linguoculturology are worked out. In this, they think that the ways of objectification of the concepts running as to be hermeneutical circle, supply linguocultural possibilities of creating speech –thinking "portrait of the object of notion". In the process of creating such a "portrait" when individually taken fragments of the character of the object is drawn, linguocognitive selection and interpretation of individually taken words, giving cultural meanings and other marked codes in the type of semantic structures of the words like idioms, phraseological units. Creation of speech portrait of this object, as to Bartminskiy, is a means of establishment of minimal meaningful elements with the language meaning. Meaningful elements appear in in the process of fixation of interpreted by the human being, features, signs, peculiarities, qualities and by the function of cognized object. Linguistist sometimes call them prototype semantics. Selected by this way signs are called profiles by Bartminskiy "Different profiles are not different meanings, but they are the ways of organizing the meaning structures of this and that meaning.... The notion of prototype can be considered as profiling of its type, accepting the fact of existence of prototype profile and its derivatives". (2006) His main difference between the conceptions of Langakar stands just in this. As to Bartminskiy profiling means "section", search of borders of social conscious. In the conceptions of Brtminskiy and Lngakar the main profiling differs: in the first conception social, ethno-cultural conscience is meant, while in the second the subjective, individual conscience is meant.

It is worth speaking of not only on different ways of conceptual analysis, but also of purposefulness of their complex usage. Domination of this tandem in this problem determines the specific feature of proper method: visual method by Lngakar and method of profiling by Bartminskiy and his school.

In conclusion ,having investigated all the points about Linguoculturology ,Linguocultural aspects of interrelation of language and culture is a major theme to studying and teaching.We can find different viewpoints and different information but the main important thing is strong connection between language and culture.

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